

NEVERFLAT Project Launches to Advance Smart and Sustainable EV Charging Across Europe

[Barcelona, 15-16 January 2025] – The NEVERFLAT project (iNnovative EV-charging EnviRonment for Future Low-cost mAss deployment) officially announces the **launch of its website and public introduction of its activities**, aiming to improve electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure across Europe.

NEVERFLAT Project Kick-off meeting, Barcelona, Spain

Funded under the **Horizon Europe Programme as part of the 2ZERO Partnership** developing affordable, inclusive, user-friendly charging infrastructure concepts and technologies NEVERFLAT brings together **13 organisations from across the EU**. The project is coordinated by Aarhus University, with technical leadership from Fundación Tekniker. Its objective is to develop a new generation of **EV charging solutions** that are more

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NEVERFLAT is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101192973.

accessible, cost-effective, and adaptable to user needs and local grid conditions.

Addressing Key Challenges

The growth of electric mobility across Europe presents several challenges, including limited charger availability, high infrastructure costs, grid stress, and a lack of intelligent user services. The NEVERFLAT project addresses these issues by **developing compact, bi-directional chargers and supporting tools based on data analytics, AI, and user-centric design.**

Project Objectives

Over the course of four years, NEVERFLAT will:

- Develop and test multimodal, compact bi-directional chargers integrated with renewable energy and local grids
- Design planning and optimisation tools using real-time data on traffic flows, energy demand, and mobility patterns
- Implement Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) and Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) services through digital twins, forecasting tools, and blockchain-based tokenization
- Explore new business models and services developed in collaboration with end users and stakeholders

Pilot Sites Across Europe

NEVERFLAT technologies will be deployed and tested in four pilot locations:

- **Berlin, Germany** – Supporting shared fleet charging and local grid management

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- **Alba Iulia, Romania** – Integrating solar energy and public charging in an educational district
- **Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain** – Demonstrating solar-powered charging and predictive grid balancing in a business park
- **Bucharest, Romania** – Combining EV charging with residential energy storage and renewables

User Interaction and Tools

NEVERFLAT will develop digital tools and mobile applications that provide users with real-time information, easy access to services, and the option to receive energy-based incentives. These tools are intended to **support both individual users and fleet operators.**

Open Collaboration and Community Engagement

The project adopts a co-creation approach, **involving users and local communities in the design and evaluation process.** This collaborative method ensures that charging infrastructure meets real-world needs and supports the broader transition to sustainable urban mobility.

Learn More

The project website is now live, offering insights into project goals, progress, and pilot activities.

- Visit the website: <https://neverflat.eu/>
- Follow NEVERFLAT on [LinkedIn](#), [X](#) and [Bluesky](#)

Contact the project team:

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